

RAD 7

**BOOK OF
ABSTRACTS**

SEVENTH
INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
ON RADIATION
IN VARIOUS FIELDS
OF RESEARCH

June 10-14, 2019
Herceg Novi
Montenegro

PUBLISHER: RAD Centre, Niš, Serbia
Bulevar Nikole Tesle 17/12, 18000 Niš, Serbia
www.rad-centre.org

FOR THE PUBLISHER: Prof. Dr. Goran Ristić

YEAR OF PUBLISHING: 2019

EDITOR: Prof. Dr. Goran Ristić

COVER DESIGN: Vladan Nikolić, PhD

TECHNICAL EDITING: Saša Trenčić, MA

PROOF-READING: Saša Trenčić, MA and Mila Trenčić, MA

CD BURNING AND COPYING: RAD Centre, Niš, Serbia

PRINT RUN: Electronic edition - 350 CDs (CD-R)

ISBN: 978-86-901150-0-6

The Seventh International Conference on Radiation in Various Fields of Research (RAD 2019) was financially supported by the Central European Initiative (CEI).

CIP - Каталогизacija y publikaciji
Narodna biblioteka Srbije, Beograd

539.16(048)(0.034.2)
57+61(048)(0.034.2)

INTERNATIONAL Conference on Radiation in Various Fields of Research (7 ; 2019 ; Herceg Novi)

Book of abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / Seventh International Conference on Radiation in Various Fields of Research, RAD 7, [RAD 2019], 10-14.06.2019 Herceg Novi, Montenegro ; [editor Goran Ristić]. - Niš : RAD Centre, 2019 (Niš : RAD Centre). - 1 elektronski optički disk (CD-ROM) ; 12 cm

Sistemski zahtevi: Nisu navedeni. - Nasl. sa naslovne strane dokumenta. - Tiraž 350.

ISBN 978-86-901150-0-6

a) Јонизујуће зрачење -- Дозиметрија -- Апстракти б) Биомедицина – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 277775116

Is there a health risk of radionuclides in drinking water from districts in Vojvodina?

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Introduction. In order to protect the human health from potential adverse effect of radionuclides, through drinking water, WHO recommended the determination of radionuclides concentrations in drinking water.

Aim. Identified trend of mean concentration of gross alpha and beta radioactivity in drinking water according to some district of region of AP Vojvodina, as well as the trend of the number of samples above the national limit value.

Method. In the six-year period (2013 – 2018), data of the concentrations of gross alpha and beta activity in drinking water from the territory of the three districts of AP Vojvodina (South Backa (SBD), Srem (SD) and South Banat (SBaD)) were analyzed. Cited districts are selected from the aspect of achieving a multi-annual continuity in terms of determining gross alpha and gross beta activity in drinking water. Total number of samples of drinking water in which it is determined gross alpha and gross beta activity by liquid scintillation counting technique in accredited laboratory of UNS was 141 in SBD, 140 in SD and 24 in SBaD. All samples, as well as samples with value below the laboratory limit value of gross alpha / beta activity (2%/68% in SBD, 1.4%/61% in SD and 4%/83% in SBaD) were analyzed with descriptive statistical method (average (determined deterministic), minimum, maximum and frequencies) and by linear trend regarding to average value for each examined year.

Results. During investigated period average value of gross alpha activity and gross beta activity was 0.06 Bq/l and 0.2 Bq/l in SBD, 0.12 Bq/l and 0.18 Bq/l in SD, 0.07 Bq/l and 0.25 Bq/l in SBaD, respectively. The value of gross alpha/beta activity in SBD, SD and SBaD ranged from <0.005/ <0.03 to 0.5/0.9 Bq/l, <0.006/ 0.028 to 1.2/0.94 Bq/l and from <0.005/ <0.03 to 0.26/0.18 Bq/l, respectively. The average annual gross alpha activity shows decreased linear trend in all district. Similar results show and average annual gross beta activity, except for SBaD. There was no exceeding national limit value for gross alpha and beta activity in SBD and SBaD. In SD there was exceeding national limit value for gross alpha activity in three samples in 2013, in two samples in 2014, and 6 samples in 2018, while there was no exceeding national limit value for gross beta activity.

Conclusion. Although there was decreasing trend of annual average gross alpha and gross beta activity in drinking water from several districts of AP Vojvodina, there was also increasing trend of samples with the exceeding national limit value for gross alpha activity in SD, which imply on possible risks for human health and necessity for continuous monitoring of drinking water.

Keywords: Drinking water, health, risk, radioactivity

Acknowledgments: The authors gratefully acknowledge the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Science of the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia for the financial support under the project "Radionuclides in drinking water and incidence of carcinoma in Vojvodina" No 142-451-2447 / 2018-01.